

Trust under pressure: Immigration governance and institutional trust in European democracies

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Abstract

This article examines the relationship between immigration and political trust in European democracies during a period marked by overlapping political, economic, and geopolitical crises. Building on performance-based theories of political trust and the distinction between trust and trustworthiness, the study argues that citizens' confidence in political institutions depends less on the salience of immigration as a political issue and more on evaluations of how effectively governments manage immigration. Using original cross-national survey data from the TRUEDEM Online Survey 2025 covering 24 European Union member states ($N \approx 29,000$), the analysis combines descriptive statistics, country-level scatterplots, and Spearman rank-order correlations. The findings reveal substantial variation in institutional trust across Europe, with generally moderate to low trust levels even in long-established democracies. While the perceived importance of managing immigration displays heterogeneous and often weak associations with political trust, evaluations of national governments' performance in managing immigration are consistently and positively correlated with trust in political institutions across all countries examined. These results provide strong support for performance-based legitimacy models and highlight the conditional nature of immigration's impact on political trust. The study contributes to debates on democratic resilience by demonstrating that immigration does not inherently undermine political trust. Instead, trust is shaped by citizens' judgments of institutional trustworthiness in addressing complex and contested policy challenges. The findings underscore the importance of effective, transparent, and accountable governance for sustaining political trust in times of crisis

Keywords

Political trust; immigration; EU governance; democratic legitimacy; performance evaluation

Introduction

Over the last two decades, European democracies have been confronted with a succession of profound and overlapping crises, including the global financial crisis, the Eurozone crisis, the rise of populism, Brexit, the COVID-19 pandemic, and most recently, the war in Ukraine and renewed violence in the Middle East. These crises have tested not only the economic and administrative capacities of European states but also the resilience of democratic institutions and the trust citizens place in them. As in other democratic systems, European political systems have entered what many scholars describe as an era of heightened polarization, declining trust, and “post-truth politics,” in which institutional authority and expert knowledge are increasingly contested (Conrad et al., 2023).

Among these crises, immigration occupies a particularly prominent position. Two recent episodes stand out for their scale and political impact. In 2015, approximately 1.2 million refugees and migrants, primarily from Syria and other conflict-affected regions, arrived in the European Union (EU). In 2022, Russia’s invasion of Ukraine led to the displacement of over six million people, many of whom sought refuge in EU member states. These large-scale population movements occurred within short time frames and generated intense political debate, media attention, and public concern. Immigration became not only a demographic or humanitarian phenomenon but also a central political issue shaping electoral competition, party systems, and public trust in political institutions (Sotiropoulos et al., 2023).

A substantial body of literature suggests that immigration crises have contributed to declining levels of political trust and rising support for populist and anti-immigration parties across Europe (Eatwell and Goodwin, 2018). Yet the mechanisms linking immigration to political trust remain contested. While some accounts emphasize cultural threat, identity politics, or economic competition, others highlight the role of political elites, media framing, and policy performance. This paper advances the latter perspective by arguing that immigration does not inherently undermine political trust; rather, its impact depends on how citizens evaluate the performance and trustworthiness of political institutions in managing immigration.

Understanding this relationship requires conceptual clarity about the notion of “crisis.” Drawing on Hay’s (1999) reformulation, crises are not merely objective disruptions but politically constructed narratives that frame certain developments as threats requiring decisive intervention. As Geddes et al. (2020) similarly argue, defining migration as a crisis is itself a political act that shapes policy responses and public perceptions. Immigration becomes politically consequential not simply because of its scale, but because of how it is framed, governed, and communicated.

It is outside the scope of this paper to present a complete and persuasive account of these competing narratives and the actual state interventions and transformations that have occurred regarding the immigration crisis (and other recent crises) at the EU level and in each separate EU Member State. However, at the political level, the general trend in Europe and the Western world is the rapid rise of the forces of the racist, anti-migrant, and ‘anti-woke’ right. Even in cases where far-right parties are not in power, the far-right agenda has greatly influenced state policies, especially on migration issues. We thus observe the paradox that those who are hostile to immigrants show low trust in political institutions, at a time when these institutions are implementing measures that increasingly restrict migration flows, the rights, and political freedoms of immigrants.

Therefore, this paper aims to explore the trends and predictors of public trust in political leaders and institutions represented as a function of their perceived trustworthiness by using fresh data stemming from the TRUEDEM project. We hypothesize that the perceptions of trustworthiness of politicians and institutions, among other things, are affected by the specific policy decisions and

overall performance of political actors. In line with this research agenda, we examine how the success or failure of governing elites to manage the immigration crisis are associated with the erosion of citizens' support to specific democratic institutions and liberal democracy as a political regime. Research on the linkages between citizens' attitudes towards political institutions and threats to democracy focuses on the democratic norms that citizens espouse or abandon during times of political crisis, e.g., times when democracy is under threat (Wallace Goodman, 2022: 6-14). The empirical strategy of this study relies on cross-national survey data from 24 EU member states by employing primarily descriptive statistics, scatterplots based on country mean scores, and bivariate analysis using Spearman's rank-order correlation coefficients ($p < .05$). This design enables an examination of whether attitudes toward immigration management are associated with citizens' trust in political institutions, both in terms of perceived importance of immigration and evaluations of governmental performance.

The literature on political trust suggests that institutional confidence is responsive to perceptions of governmental effectiveness in salient policy domains, including immigration, which has become a key arena of political contestation across Europe. In line with this framework and with the analytical approach of this study, three hypotheses are formulated.

H1: Immigration Salience Hypothesis. Higher perceived importance of managing immigration in one's country is associated with lower levels of trust in political institutions. In empirical terms, this hypothesis implies a negative Spearman correlation coefficient between the importance of managing immigration and trust in political institutions. Scatterplots of country means are expected to show a downward pattern in contexts where greater concern about immigration coincides with lower institutional trust.

H2: Performance Evaluation Hypothesis. More positive evaluations of the national government's performance in managing immigration are associated with higher levels of trust in political institutions. Accordingly, this hypothesis predicts a positive and statistically significant Spearman correlation between evaluations of governmental performance and institutional trust. At the descriptive level, countries scoring higher in perceived performance are expected to cluster toward higher levels of trust in the scatterplots.

H3: Consistency and Strength Hypothesis. The relationship between trust in political institutions and evaluations of governmental performance in managing immigration will be stronger and more consistent across countries than the relationship between trust and the perceived importance of immigration. In methodological terms, this hypothesis anticipates more robust, higher-magnitude, and more uniformly significant Spearman coefficients for the performance variable compared to the importance variable. It also expects clearer and more stable "uphill" patterns in the relevant scatterplots based on country-level means.

Together, these hypotheses are directly aligned with the analytical procedures employed in this study. They allow for systematic testing of whether immigration functions primarily as a source of political pressure, reducing institutional/political trust, or as a domain through which effective governmental performance can sustain or enhance trust in political institutions.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. The next section develops the conceptual framework by discussing political trust, trustworthiness, and the distinction between diffuse and specific political support, followed by a theoretical discussion of the links between immigration, political trust, and democratic legitimacy. The subsequent sections present the data, methods, and empirical strategy, followed by the statistical analysis of cross-national survey evidence from 24 EU member states. The paper concludes with a discussion of the findings and their implications for democratic governance and political trust in times of crisis.

Diffuse and specific support to political institutions

The linkages between political trust and democracy have long been debated. Trust towards the democratic regime itself, its institutions, and elected authorities is not taken for granted and may fluctuate, but without such trust, in contrast to other political regimes, democracies cannot survive. The risk comes from a break in the link between citizens and political institutions. This link is political trust. Normative political theory has elaborated on this theme (Hardin, 2006; Warren, 2010). While theorists have conceptualized “political trust” in several ways, a succinct definition of the concept is the following: political trust is “*a summary judgment that the system is responsive and will do what is right even in the absence of constant scrutiny*” (Miller and Listhaug, 1990: 358). Yet this definition conceals important conceptual distinctions that are crucial for understanding contemporary patterns of trust and distrust.

Following Norris (2015; 2017; 2022), it is essential to distinguish between confidence, trust, and trustworthiness. Confidence refers to beliefs about an institution’s technical capacity to perform tasks, whereas trust involves expectations about benevolent motivation, integrity, and fairness. Trustworthiness, in turn, refers to whether an institution or actor deserves trust based on its past performance and adherence to normative standards. Importantly, low trust does not necessarily signal democratic decay; it may reflect a rational and normatively desirable form of skepticism toward institutions perceived as corrupt, incompetent, or unaccountable.

These distinctions align closely with Easton’s (1965; 1975) influential framework of political support. Easton differentiated between specific support, short-term evaluations of incumbent officeholders, and diffuse support, which refers to deeper, more enduring attachments to political institutions and regime principles. Norris (2017) further refined this framework by distinguishing five levels of political support: the political community, regime principles, regime performance, regime institutions, and political authorities.

Empirical studies of political trust typically focus on evaluations of regime institutions and authorities, as these dimensions are most sensitive to policy performance and political crises. This paper follows that tradition by examining trust in core political institutions and linking it to evaluations of immigration governance. Immigration is particularly well suited for this analysis because it simultaneously tests institutional competence, normative commitments, and responsiveness to public concerns.

The theoretical logic of the connection between immigration, political trust, and democracy

There are various perspectives on the connection between immigration, political trust, and democracy. They are briefly discussed here to allow for a comprehensive overview that includes approaches based on political theory (at the beginning of this section) and approaches relying on theoretically grounded empirical research (in the second part of this section).

First, there is a theoretical argument that puts immigration at the center of the domestic politics of European democracies (Michael, 2021). It is an overly critical, if not radical, current of thought. It departs from the view that migration policy is a tool that European governments have used to reaffirm state sovereignty at the expense of democracy. Governments have made a return to national identity politics on purpose. To strengthen national identity, governments have turned against migrants and refugees and have closed the borders of Europe. In this process, Western European democracies “have re-imagined themselves as cohesive societies” (Michael, 2021: 3).

Similarly, the challenges which European democracies face cannot be understood out of the context of marginalization of migrants and refugees (Michael, 2021: 8): the fear, rather than the actual

numbers, of incoming migrants and refugees sparks a series of reactions leading to a negative impact on democracy. Governments implement anti-immigration policies that violate the human rights of migrants and refugees encapsulated in the 1951 UN Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees. Moreover, governments opt for short-term securitization approaches to long-term approaches to managing causes of immigration (Michael, 2021: 4-5). European governments have taken up the task to assert national sovereignty through the regulation of and restrictions on migration. By doing so, they particularly want to exclude Muslim migrants and refugees. The result is an “identarian closure” of European democracies and a “corrosive effects on civic trust and solidarity but, more importantly, also the [undermining of] the foundations of liberal democracy” (Michael, 2021: 4-8).

There is a less polemical theoretical argument that links immigration with political trust, claiming that the former negatively impacts the latter. The argument departs from a wider, global, analytical view. In some detail, large-scale external and economic challenges to European democracies, such as globalization and de-industrialization, have brought a series of social and economic effects. The latter, in turn, have provoked political effects, including the rise of populism and the transition to “authoritarian democracy” which is reflected in restrictive migration policies (Campani, 2019: 35). The aforesaid external and economic developments have contributed to the decline of well-being of the lower-income groups, to rising unemployment, and to economic crisis in Europe. Populist parties have grasped the opportunity to attract voters who are the victims of the crisis. They embrace democracy, but not liberalism, as shown in the abrasive shifts of populist policies in reaction to the scale and timing of migration. The shifts negatively impact classical democratic norms such as human solidarity, openness, and diversity (Campani, 2019: 35).

However, not only populist, but also other European governments have tried to manage these developments by imposing economic policies of austerity and imposing restrictions on migration, as migration inflows were perceived to be a destructive aspect of globalization. For example, during and after the Eurozone crisis, Italian governments changed their migration policy. In 2013-2017 they had adopted a humanitarian approach to migrants and refugees under PMs E. Letta and M. Renzi. After 2017, however, they adopted a security-driven approach to immigration (Campani, 2019: 42-43). The combination of technocratic management of the economy (e.g., the Monti government in Italy) with the restrictive management of immigration contributes to a transition of democracy to post-democracy, in the sense Colin Crouch uses the term (Crouch, 2013). Democratic institutions are, along the way, rendered pure formality. Meanwhile, small circles of interconnected political and business elites put themselves in the driver’s seat of contemporary democracies.

Further on, legal theorists have also underlined how difficult it is for European democracies, which rely on the rule of law, to manage irregular migration (Kuzelewska et al., 2018). Such migration poses multiple legal and ethical challenges to European democracies. Their failure to respond to these challenges is manifested in the numerous cases related to immigration, which the European Court of Human Rights (ECHR) has considered and the Council of Europe’s actions to monitor the fundamental rights of migrants and refugees (Kuzelewska, et al., 2018: xxii).

While the authors cited above develop a theoretical viewpoint, there is a body of empirical research on immigration and political trust consisting of national case studies and cross-national studies. This empirical research on the impact of immigration on political trust in specific European countries is theoretically grounded. The authors of such empirical studies adopt analytical explanations for why immigration influences political trust. Their arguments can be summarized as follows: political attitudes (including trust in political institutions) of citizens who, for various reasons, perceive immigration as a risk factor (or a threat) become subject to citizens’ (dis)satisfaction with how

successful the political institutions have been in dealing with immigration. If citizens perceive that the institutions and the elected officials who manage them fail in stemming immigration, then the citizens' political trust decreases. Distrust towards institutions and elected officials may spill over to distrust towards the democratically organized political community.

This theoretical argument ties well with the conceptualization of political trust by Norris (2022) and with the theoretical framework of the TRUEDEM project. This conceptualization understands political trust as a function of the perception of trustworthiness of political institutions. While trust is a quality of the individual, trustworthiness is a feature of dyadic relationships (Norris 2022). The individual makes rational judgements not only on trust, but also on trustworthiness, which is a useful way to understand the dyadic relationship between an individual and a political institution on which he or she passes a rational judgement. Thus, trustworthiness depends on how able the institutions are to construct a political environment providing citizens with guaranteed political rights, ensured economic prosperity, equality, and well-being and moreover an environment informed by ethical, just, fair, and transparent standards (Zmerli 2014; Mishler and Rose, 2005).

Figure 1. Heuristic model of skeptical judgement of trustworthiness.

Source: Norris (2022:42).

The concept of trustworthiness is particularly important for understanding how trust is built, and in the context of TRUEDEM research, it is fundamental for conceptualizing the dynamic process through which political trust is built (or eroded). As explained in the conceptual framework of the TRUEDEM proposal (see project website), citizens recurrently evaluate new evidence (e.g. new policies, reforms, adoption of new legislation) based on good governance criteria. This repeated process is

mediated by individual-level characteristics of the citizens (education, cognitive skills) and by factors of the social, political, and cultural environment in which citizens are embedded. The following figure, drawn on Norris (2022: 42), is a model of how the individual, placed in a certain societal, cultural, and information environment, uses their analytical, cognitive, and information-processing skills to rationally develop perceptions on the performance of institutions or agencies and to form skeptical judgements of the trustworthiness of institutions or agencies.

This theoretical framework can be applied to the case of immigration and political trust as follows (Figure 2). On the left, performance indicators are represented by immigration as an objective phenomenon (i.e. the actual number of foreign nationals arriving in the country) and the existing migration policies and regulations at the EU, countries and local (regional) levels that regulation the process of immigration, including practical aspects such as accommodation, financial support, healthcare, and integration of immigrants, including schooling, employment, language courses etc. The public perceptions of immigration are then formed under the influence of individual factors (education, access to information, choice of media sources, own social and economic status) and society-level factors, including information environment, media reporting, and media pluralism.

Figure 2. Theoretical framework on interplay of immigration and political trust.

Source: TRUEDEM project team, original research.

As outlined in the subsequent sections, perceptions of immigration are largely subject to one's negative evaluation of newcomers in categories of "risk factor/ threat" – or rather positive evaluation as an addition to the local national community that would enrich and improve life in the country. Negative vs positive perceptions of immigration would then comprise a cumulative assessment of the threat/ contribution along several dimensions, including a) national identity; b) value system and culture; c) economy. Societies with actively pronounced gender equality norms might be concerned about immigrants from traditional, patriarchal societies. Societies where a certain religion (e.g. Catholicism) became an integral part of the national identity might be concerned about immigrants with a different religious background (e.g. Muslims). Societies that go through economic hardships and have a high level of unemployment will likely be cautious about immigrants, perceiving them as competition on the labor market. This link is also functional at the level of individuals or social groups within the society.

The model suggests that after the citizens developed their perceptions on the extent to which political institutions and elected authorities rise to the immigration challenge and deal with it, they use this information to judge the trustworthiness of these institutions and authorities. Thus, the interaction of perceived threats with policy responses impacts how citizens consider the EU, national, and local governments, as well as other political institutions (the parliament, the public administration, and political parties) as (un)trustworthy. The assessment of trustworthiness, in turn, influences the level of political trust of citizens towards the governing and other political institutions. Individuals' civic knowledge, education level, cognitive skills, and critical thinking, as well as media reports on immigration and, foremost, the type of migration policy in the country, serve as key mediators between immigration and its implications for political trust.

It should be noted that the process of assessment of immigration and decision about (un)trustworthiness of the political institutions is cyclic: as new immigrants arrive, as the migration policy changes, or if changes occur in one of the individual/societal factors, public perceptions of immigration and public trust in the authorities might change. Finally, political trust (measured through public opinion surveys) can also be used to inform the authorities on the need to update their migration policies in response to the growing public (dis)satisfaction.

Method of research

The analysis is based on the TRUEDEM Online Survey 2025 for the following 24 European countries: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czechia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain and Sweden (Haerpfer et al. 2026). In the summer of 2025, the TRUEDEM teams conducted a cross-national online survey on political trust and democratic attitudes in 24 EU member states. In each country, approximately 1,200 respondents were interviewed, with 1,500 in France and Germany, resulting in nearly 29,000 participants in total. The national samples were designed to reflect the demographic structure of each population, ensuring comparability across countries.

The questionnaire covers a broad range of themes related to democracy and trust. It measures confidence in parliaments, governments, political parties, the judiciary, the European Union, and international organizations, alongside perceptions of competence, fairness, accountability, and integrity. Respondents were asked to assess government performance in areas such as the economy, healthcare, security, and the environment, and to express their levels of satisfaction with democracy both nationally and at the EU level. Beyond institutional trust, the survey explores political orientations and values, ideological positions, support for populism, and perceptions of polarization. It examines different forms of political participation, including voting, protest, and online engagement, as well as media use, exposure to misinformation, civic knowledge, political efficacy, and support for democratic norms and civil liberties. To complement these modules, the survey also included survey experiments examining how issue framing and context influence citizens' perceptions of trust.

In Table 1, a summary of the participants' demographic and social characteristics is presented. As shown, gender was almost equally distributed in most countries where the samples included more men than women. In the survey the participants also had three more options, transgender, non-binary and other, these categories had no responses in the case of Portugal, in most countries were from 0.1% to 0.5% and only in the case of Bulgaria was 1.5%. The mean age ranged from 47 to 50. Married participants ranged from 18.3% (Finland) to 52.3% (Romania). Those that had no education or early childhood education (ISCED 0), that had completed primary education (ISCED 1), lower secondary education (ISCED 2), up to upper secondary education (ISCED 3) ranged from 35.1% in the case of

Ireland to 77.1% in the case of Italy. Participants in paid work (including full time employee (30 hours a week or more), part time employee (less than 30 hours a week) and also self-employed) ranged from 49.7% (Italy) to 79.4% (Bulgaria).

Table 1. The demographic and social characteristics of participants: TRUEDEM Online Survey, 2025.

Country	N	Men (%)	Women (%)	Age (\bar{x} and SD)	Married (%)	Education (%)	In paid work (%)
Austria	1222	51.2	48.3	47.7 (16.6)	43.0	55.6	58.3
Belgium	1217	50.7	48.8	47.8 (17.5)	41.7	59.8	51.6
Bulgaria	1200	46.9	51.5	49.4 (14.7)	37.0	71.5	79.4
Croatia	1207	52.1	47.7	48.9 (16.4)	45.4	64.3	62.9
Czechia	1217	51.0	48.5	49.1 (16.6)	38.4	60.9	61.4
Denmark	1200	50.5	49.2	48.4 (17.3)	31.6	64.7	60.0
Estonia	1202	50.8	49.1	50.4 (17.3)	28.8	51.3	69.5
Finland	1202	50.8	49.1	47.9 (16.2)	18.3	55.9	52.8
France	1502	51.9	47.8	48.7 (16.6)	44.1	62.5	54.1
Germany	1501	50.6	49	48.2 (16.9)	42.2	67.6	56.4
Greece	1201	51.3	48.5	49.3 (15.4)	47.2	60.8	68.2
Hungary	1208	52.1	47.5	48.6 (16.7)	35.9	64.9	59.4
Ireland	1204	50.9	48.9	47.1 (16.1)	44.1	35.1	70.1
Italy	1127	51.5	48.3	50.0 (15.8)	46.7	77.1	49.7
Latvia	1223	54.7	45.1	47.5 (13.9)	32.8	54.7	72.1
Lithuania	1375	54.1	45.7	48.1 (15.2)	42.2	53.2	74.4
Netherlands	1200	50.7	49.2	48.7 (17.8)	44.9	57.8	57.5
Poland	1203	52.0	47.7	48.7 (16.2)	38.2	60.8	64.1
Portugal	1208	52.8	47.2	49.2 (15.5)	40.6	70.9	72.9
Romania	1201	51.8	48.1	47.7 (15.4)	52.3	65.8	55.9
Slovakia	1202	51.4	48.3	47.3 (15.8)	38.8	72.3	66.2
Slovenia	1219	49.8	49.9	49.9 (15.6)	35.5	71.5	65.1
Spain	1215	51.3	48.5	49.4 (15.6)	47.5	58.4	59.9
Sweden	1212	49.7	50.1	48.5 (17.4)	34.4	48.9	60.1

In the analyses, we used the constructed variable Trust in Political Institutions (0–100), named in the dataset as “trust_pol”. This variable is an index capturing generalized trust in core political institutions (national government, regional government, parliament, parties, courts/judiciary, head of state, head of government, and elections). Constructed on a 1–4 response scale and normalized to 0–100; higher scores indicate greater trust. The index formula is the following: $\text{trust_pol} = (\text{SUM}(\text{Q1}, \text{Q2}, \text{Q3}, \text{Q4}, \text{Q5}, \text{Q6}, \text{Q7}, \text{Q8}) - 8) * (100 / 24)$. The range is from 0 (if all eight items = 1) to 100 (if all eight items = 4). Higher values denote greater trust in political institutions.

We also used two questions measuring the management of immigration. The first question is about the importance of managing immigration (*What is the importance of the following problems in your country? – Managing immigration*), measured on a 4-point scale, from very unimportant to very

important. The second question is about the performance of national governments in the management of immigration (*How would you evaluate the national government's performance in each of the following areas? – Managing immigration*), measured on a 5-point scale, from very bad to very good.

The empirical analysis proceeds in three steps, combining univariate, bivariate, and comparative cross-national approaches. First, descriptive statistics are used to map overall levels of trust in political institutions and public attitudes toward immigration management across the 24 EU member states. Second, bivariate associations are examined using Spearman's order correlation coefficients to assess the strength and direction of the relationship between political trust and the two immigration-related variables: perceived importance of immigration management and evaluations of government performance in this domain. Third, country-level scatterplots based on mean scores are employed to visualize cross-national variation and to identify clustering patterns among countries with similar attitudinal profiles. Statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics Version 27.

The univariate results indicate substantial cross-national variation in institutional trust. While Nordic and northwestern European countries display comparatively higher mean levels of trust, no country approaches the upper end of the scale, suggesting a generalized climate of skepticism toward political institutions across Europe. This finding is consistent with previous research documenting the erosion of political trust even in long-established democracies (Norris, 2011; van der Meer and Zmerli, 2017). Importantly, the distribution of trust scores does not simply mirror economic development or regime type within the EU, indicating that issue-specific evaluations—such as immigration governance—may play a distinct role.

Turning to immigration salience, descriptive results show that managing immigration is widely perceived as an important or very important issue across all countries. This confirms that immigration constitutes a shared concern across Europe, irrespective of actual immigration levels or national policy traditions. However, high salience alone does not translate uniformly into political discontent, suggesting that issue importance captures attention and concern rather than dissatisfaction per se.

The bivariate analyses reveal a clear asymmetry between the two immigration-related variables. Evaluations of national governments' performance in managing immigration are consistently and positively associated with trust in political institutions across all countries. The magnitude of these correlations is moderate to strong, indicating that performance assessments in this policy domain function as a key driver of institutional trust. This finding lends strong empirical support to the Performance Evaluation Hypothesis (H2) and confirms expectations derived from performance-based theories of political legitimacy.

By contrast, the relationship between the perceived importance of immigration management and political trust is weaker, less consistent, and often statistically insignificant. Where significant, the association is predominantly negative, suggesting that heightened concern about immigration may coincide with lower trust in contexts where governments are perceived as ineffective or unresponsive. However, the presence of positive correlations in a subset of countries indicates that immigration salience can coexist with higher trust when citizens perceive institutions as capable and legitimate. These patterns support the Consistency and Strength Hypothesis (H3), as performance evaluations display greater robustness and cross-national uniformity than issue salience.

Additional exploratory analyses comparing country clusters suggest that institutional trust is highest where immigration performance evaluations are relatively positive, regardless of the absolute importance attributed to immigration. This reinforces the conclusion that trust is shaped less by the politicization of immigration itself and more by citizens' judgments of how well political institutions manage politically sensitive challenges.

Figure 3. Mean values of trust in political institutions [0-100 scale], TRUEDEM Online Survey.

In Figure 3, political trust ranged from 29 (Romania) to 59 (Denmark). In most countries the mean values lie between 40 and 50, values below 50 corresponding to mistrust towards political institutions. Only 5 countries have mean values over 50, the Netherlands (53), Finland (53), Ireland (54), Sweden (56), and Denmark (59). But even those countries are closer to 50 than 100, which shows that no country seems to trust the political institutions.

Managing immigration is very important in most countries, from 37.3% in Slovakia up to 63.7% in the case of Germany. Managing immigration as very unimportant has in all countries low percentages, from 1.8% in the case of Croatia up to 7.8% in the case of France (see Figure 4).

In most countries, respondents do not evaluate as 'very good' their national government's performance in managing immigration. Except for the Hungarians where 13.4% evaluate their government more than 10% that the national government is very good in managing immigration, all the others 23 countries evaluate their government with very good below 10% of the respondents from 3.3% in the case of Croatia and up to 9.8% in the cases of Denmark and Germany. Very bad evaluation seems to have more respondents as 13.4% in the case of Slovakia up to 32.6% in the case of France respond that. Neither good nor bad evaluate many respondents their country government in managing immigration, with 21.6% of the Germans respond that up to 38.5% Lithuanians (see Figure 5).

In Figure 6, the scatterplot of the mean scores on trust in political institutions and the perceived importance in the country of managing immigration is presented across all the 24 countries. As shown, an "uphill" pattern is detected, indicating a positive relationship between the two variables. Countries such as Romania, Slovenia, Czechia, and France appear to "cluster" closer to the regression line, suggesting a more consistent alignment between higher perceived salience of immigration management and levels of institutional trust. Although variation exists across national contexts, the

overall pattern supports that where immigration is perceived as a national issue, trust in political institutions tends to be comparatively higher.

Figure 4. Importance in the country: Managing immigration, TRUEDEM Online Survey.

Figure 5. National government's performance: Managing immigration, TRUEDEM Online Survey.

Figure 6. Scatterplot of the mean scores on trust in political institutions and the importance of managing immigration, TRUEDEM Online Survey, 2025.

Figure 7. Figure caption Calibri 10, left-aligned, at 1.15 rows.

In Figure 7, the scatterplot of the mean scores on trust in political institutions and the evaluation of their national government's performance in managing immigration is presented. The scatter plot again reveals a clear positive association between the two constructs. Countries such as Bulgaria, Belgium, and the Netherlands closely follow the trend line, while Denmark, Ireland, Sweden and Czechia "cluster" nearby, indicating relatively strong correspondence between trust in political institutions and the governmental implementation in managing immigration. These findings suggest that governments' better evaluation in handling migration tends to evaluate higher levels of institutional trust.

Table 2. Spearman's correlation coefficient of opinions towards managing immigration and trust in political institutions, TRUEDEM Online Survey.

Country	Importance in your country: Managing immigration	National government's performance: Managing immigration
Austria	-.073	.540
Belgium	.005**	.460
Bulgaria	-.063*	.470
Croatia	-.098	.473
Czechia	-.145	.557
Denmark	.114	.392
Estonia	-.055**	.453
Finland	.029**	.415
France	.025**	.504
Germany	-.002**	.492
Greece	-.033**	.524
Hungary	.251	.593
Ireland	-.053**	.477
Italy	.003**	.493
Latvia	-.002**	.454
Lithuania	.070*	.407
Netherlands	-.044**	.445
Poland	-.060*	.517
Portugal	-.006**	.399
Romania	-.060**	.486
Slovakia	.145	.397
Slovenia	-.071*	.474
Spain	-.005**	.423
Sweden	.060*	.434

Note: ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$.

In Table 3, the correlation coefficients of the two questions of managing immigration and trust in the political institutions are presented. The correlation coefficients of the importance in the country of the "problem" managing immigration were not significant in the cases of Belgium, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, the Netherlands, Portugal, and Romania. The correlation coefficients were significant only in the cases of Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czechia, Denmark, Hungary, Lithuania, Poland, Slovakia, and Slovenia. As shown in most of these cases, the

relationship is negative, suggesting that perceiving immigration management as a particularly important issue is associated with lower institutional trust. However, in a smaller subset of countries, including Belgium, Denmark, Hungary and Lithuania the relationship is positive, indicating contextual variability in how issue salience relates to trust.

As shown, in all cases, correlation coefficients of evaluating the national government's performance in managing immigration were significant and positive and ranged from .392 (Denmark) to .593 (Hungary). Correlation coefficients of how important managing immigration is in respondents' countries were significant except in Belgium, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, the Netherlands, Portugal, Romania, and Spain. In all countries where the correlation coefficients were significant, all the correlations were negative except in the cases of Denmark, Hungary, Lithuania, Slovenia, and Sweden.

Discussion and conclusion

The findings of this study contribute to the broader literature on political trust by demonstrating that attitudes toward immigration management are closely intertwined with citizens' confidence in political institutions across European democracies. The analysis shows that although the perceived importance of immigration management exhibits heterogeneous associations with political trust across countries, evaluations of governmental performance in this domain display a remarkably consistent and positive relationship with institutional trust. This pattern aligns with theoretical arguments that link trust to performance-based legitimacy, suggesting that citizens' confidence in political institutions is shaped not only by normative commitments to democracy but also by perceived governmental effectiveness in addressing salient policy challenges (Easton, 1975; Norris, 2011; van der Meer and Zmerli, 2017).

The finding that performance evaluations are strongly and positively correlated with institutional trust across all 24 countries underscores the significance of outcome-based assessments in sustaining political legitimacy. As previous research has argued, political trust is often contingent and responsive to citizens' judgments about competence, fairness, and problem-solving capacity (Hetherington, 2005; Rothstein and Stolle, 2008). Immigration constitutes a highly politicized and emotionally charged policy area in contemporary Europe, frequently associated with debates about national identity, social cohesion, and economic security. Consequently, citizens' perceptions of how effectively governments manage immigration appear to serve as a key heuristic in evaluating the broader trustworthiness of political institutions.

By contrast, the relationship between the perceived importance of immigration and institutional trust is more complex and context-dependent. In several countries, a higher perceived importance of immigration is associated with lower trust, which may reflect heightened concern, insecurity, or dissatisfaction with political elites' responsiveness to public demands. In other contexts, however, greater salience correlates positively with trust, possibly indicating that in environments where governments are perceived as capable and proactive, heightened concern does not necessarily translate into distrust. These divergent patterns suggest that issue salience alone does not uniformly erode or strengthen trust; rather, its impact appears mediated by institutional capacity, political discourse, and national policy contexts (Citrin and Sides, 2008; Levi and Stoker, 2000).

These findings speak directly to broader debates about democratic resilience in times of crisis. Much of the critical literature suggests that restrictive migration policies and securitization strategies undermine democratic norms and civic trust (Michael, 2021; Campani, 2019). While this concern remains valid, the present analysis indicates that citizens' trust judgments are not driven solely by normative opposition to restrictive policies or by the presence of immigration itself. Rather, trust

appears to hinge on whether institutions are perceived as acting coherently, transparently, and effectively within the bounds of democratic governance. In this sense, low trust may reflect not democratic decay per se, but rational scepticism toward institutions judged as untrustworthy—a distinction emphasized in Norris’s work on “healthy mistrust.”

Overall, the results highlight a crucial distinction: immigration as a perceived problem does not automatically undermine confidence in political institutions, but how governments are judged to handle it does. This finding carries important implications for democratic governance in Europe. In an era characterized by polarization, populist contestation, and mounting pressures on liberal democratic institutions, maintaining and enhancing political trust may depend heavily on governments’ ability to convincingly demonstrate competence and effectiveness in managing complex policy challenges such as immigration. Future research could extend this work by incorporating longitudinal data to assess causal dynamics over time, exploring individual-level mechanisms behind these associations and also to examine causal dynamics and explore how shifts in immigration policy, media framing, and crisis narratives shape trust over time.

Several implications follow from this study. First, governments seeking to sustain political trust should prioritize not only controlling immigration flows but also communicating policy goals, constraints, and outcomes in a transparent and credible manner. Second, the findings caution against alarmist narratives that portray immigration as inherently corrosive to democracy; such narratives risk obscuring the central role of institutional performance.

In conclusion, this study demonstrates that immigration affects political trust primarily through citizens’ evaluations of institutional trustworthiness rather than through issue salience alone. In times of crisis, trust in democracy depends less on the absence of contentious issues and more on the perceived capacity of political institutions to manage them effectively, fairly, and in accordance with democratic principles. Finally, future research should extend this analysis longitudinally to examine causal dynamics and explore how shifts in immigration policy, media framing, and crisis narratives shape trust over time.

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